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MODERN OPPORTUNITIES FOR THE INTEGRATION OF TECHNOLOGIES INTO THE MEDIA AND THEIR ROLE IN IMPROVING THE EFFICIENCY OF THE MEDIA

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Abstract: This article explores the integration of modern information and communication technologies into the media sector and their role in enhancing media efficiency. It examines how technological convergence is transforming the media environment, enabling the emergence of new media formats through digital platforms and interactive user engagement. The study also highlights the application of artificial intelligence, digital editing, cloud technologies, and real-time analytics in modern journalism and broadcasting.

Key words: media convergence, digital technologies, mass media, artificial intelligence, interactivity, information delivery, technological integration.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada zamonaviy axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalarining ommaviy axborot vositalariga integratsiyalashuvi, ularning samaradorlikni oshirishdagi o'рни hamda media kontentni ishlab chiqarish va tarqatishdagi imkoniyatlari tahlil qilinadi. Texnologik konvergensiya sharoitida media muhitining o'zgarishi, raqamli platformalarning ommalashuvi va foydalanuvchilarning interaktiv ishtiroki asosida yangi media formatlari shakllanmoqda. Maqolada shuningdek, sun'iy intellekt, raqamli tahrir, bulutli texnologiyalar va real vaqtli tahlil vositalarining ommaviy axborot vositalari faoliyatiga integratsiyasi yoritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: media konvergensiya, raqamli texnologiyalar, ommaviy axborot vositalari, sun'iy intellekt, interaktivlik, axborot uzatish, texnologik integratsiya.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается интеграция современных информационно-коммуникационных технологий в сферу средств массовой информации и их роль в повышении эффективности медиа. Анализируется влияние технологической конвергенции на трансформацию медиасреды, появление новых форматов медиаконтента на цифровых платформах, а также участие пользователей в интерактивном взаимодействии. Особое внимание уделено использованию искусственного интеллекта, цифрового редактирования, облачных технологий и инструментов анализа в реальном времени в современной журналистике.

Ключевые слова: медийная конвергенция, цифровые технологии, СМИ, искусственный интеллект, интерактивность, передача информации, технологическая интеграция.

INTRODUCTION

The term "media convergence" ^[1] refers to the merging of various media technologies, content, and devices into a single environment. This phenomenon is manifested in the way all types of media forms merge into one digital environment due to the development of information technology. Media convergence is the result of new realities in editorial activities. If we turn to history, it becomes clear that the newspapers that appeared in print at the beginning of the 17th century existed independently and were self-sufficient until the end of the 20th century.

The peculiarity of the media text is that it integrates various verbal and non-verbal codes into a single communicative whole. The media text has acquired well-known universal features and can be included in different media structures: in the form of a classic text; audio sequence; illustrations.

In conditions of convergence, the capacity and influence of verbal sound, visual, and multi-layered media texts increase markedly. Modern technologies provide unlimited circulation of mass information in space and

time, allow it to be delivered to a wide and segmented audience, enable individuals to participate in the creation of media texts, and facilitate interactive, multi-vector communication [2].

Figure 1: Multi-vector communication

LITERATURE REVIEW

In the 21st century, the integration of technology into media has significantly transformed the methods and efficiency of information dissemination. Scholars have analyzed these changes from various perspectives, ranging from economic frameworks to typological and structural models of communication. Guslyakova (2021) explores the typological characteristics of information transmission in both print and electronic media, emphasizing that modern technology enables a more interactive and immediate exchange of information, distinguishing today's media from its traditional, linear counterparts. Her research underscores how the transition from print to digital has necessitated new strategies in content production and audience engagement.

Vartanova (2003), in her work on media economics, examines the operational models of foreign media systems, highlighting how technological advancement has not only improved media efficiency but also led to structural changes in funding models, content distribution, and audience segmentation. Her insights reveal that technological integration goes hand-in-hand with economic adaptability in the media industry.

Expanding on innovation, Gershanok and Kuzovnikov (2019) present a convergent-divergent model that adds depth to the innovation process within media systems. Their model illustrates how convergence – the blending of different types of media – and divergence – the emergence of new formats and platforms – work simultaneously to create a more flexible and scalable media environment.

Lukina's edited volume (2016) provides practical insights into internet media, particularly focusing on digital journalism, multimedia storytelling, and user interactivity. The textbook emphasizes the pedagogical and professional dimensions of digital tools, offering strategies for training future journalists to be technologically competent and creatively adaptive. Khudoykulov (2010), representing perspectives from Central Asia, discusses journalism and publicism in the context of socio-political realities. He highlights the role of technological tools in shaping public discourse and increasing access to timely and reliable information, particularly in developing media environments.

Finally, McLuhan's seminal work *Understanding Media* (1964) remains foundational. His concept of media as "extensions of man" provides the philosophical underpinning for discussions on how digital technologies extend human capabilities, reshape perception, and influence societal structures. McLuhan's ideas serve as a timeless lens through which modern media transformation can be contextualized.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Speaking about changes in journalistic creativity, it is important to understand that these transformations are profound and irreversible. This is due to the fact that today communication takes place simultaneously through printed, electronic, multimedia, oral, written, real and virtual media. Due to these changes, it is inevitable that the processes of digitalization and convergence in the media increasingly affect the creative activity of journalists – the specifics of their interaction with technology and information delivery channels are changing [3], with the audience and other subjects of communication. High-tech methods of cognition, collection, processing and transmission of information are emerging, and a new culture of the information world is being formed.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Convergent journalism integrates these environments, which leads to the emergence, along with traditional journalistic genres, of genres of other functional styles. Under the influence of the Internet environment, old genres are being transformed and new ones are emerging. The language and style of texts acquire characteristic features due to the peculiarities of the functional environment. For example, texts based on new prin-

principles of communication and perception encourage the recipient not only to react, but also to respond in real time. The audience's activity is increasing not only in consumption, but also in the production of texts, and the degree of its involvement in media and forms of communication is expanding.

At the same time, online versions of newspapers have become an additional synthesized and universal medium for texts. They provide a variety of content in a qualitatively better way, at a new system level, which makes it possible to expand the audience and use interactive tools for interacting with communication sources, consumers and advertisers. This contributes to the promotion of both the print edition and the electronic version to the media market, and in general, to the expansion of information flows, personalization of the interaction process, and leads, so to speak, to point-to-point communication. Convergent processes determine the interpenetration of communicative environments^[4]. In turn, the multimedia environment of the Internet and personalized communication strategies allow communication subjects – journalists and the audience, as well as other participants in the communication act – to create texts in various forms, taking into account communication conditions, mutual interests and needs.

Thus, in general, the convergence of traditional media, modern information technologies and methods have significantly influenced the nature of a journalist's communicative, creative activity, and its focus on the audience. The technological characteristics of the network, which are expanding day by day, have begun to significantly affect the quality of information and the ways it is presented. The Internet has become a channel and a virtual environment for personal and business contacts, promotions and communications. Being a means of information dissemination, the global network has become at the same time a unique tool that is taken into account when preparing content, an indispensable "colleague" in the work of the editorial staff. Creative workers realized that being a convergent journalist means being able to create journalistic texts for both traditional and online media at the same time, use various strategies and forms of communication with the audience and other subjects of professional activity, that is, to carry out fundamentally new subject–subject relations.

Under the influence of trends in the personalization of mass communication, many journalists have started blogging, created personal Internet pages, and serve as moderators. For journalists, the Internet environment has become an additional source of information, a means of communicating with a narrowly segmented audience, and a place of creative fulfillment. Mass communication is shifting towards the mass-individual side. As can be seen from the above, today almost all types of print media have online versions – that is, electronic periodicals that are created thanks to digital technologies and function as websites in the WWW environment. Their content consists of printed (offline) texts and original texts, which have their own characteristics due to the virtual environment^[5]. Such an electronic periodical corresponds to the main typological features of its printed counterpart, but at the same time, it has unique characteristics typical for online media.

Online versions embody the most daring creative solutions, offer additional services to the audience, services to advertisers, and implement various commercial and social projects. Despite their new specifics, they continue to retain the characteristics of traditional media. Unlike the original printed formats, however, the characteristic features of the online versions of newspapers include low cost, cost-effectiveness, mobility, and flexibility.

It should be noted that the personalized segmentation of the audience differs from that of its printed counterpart and involves the expansion of the circle of non-professional authors. At the same time, this increases the level of trust between the author and the audience – "personification" or "parasocial relationships". The potential audience of a print publication can become the actual audience of the online version. In addition, online versions are an effective sociological tool that allows the analysis of the audience composition, its preferences, and its movement trajectory on the site. They also involve readers in co-creation and serve as an additional channel for the editorial board to conduct commercial communication and PR activities.

The relationship between the texts of the printed newspaper and the online version can be observed, which stimulates the activity and interest of readers. Print media websites are typically designed in the style of new information design, characterized by conciseness, clarity, and enhanced functionality.

In turn, print media remain the primary "suppliers" of content. They are more analytical and possess additional capabilities for interaction, including with social institutions and international audiences. When considered in relation to journalistic technologies, the electronic version of a periodical can logically be regarded as an online project or information resource that enhances the efficiency of a converged editorial office.

A convergent environment fosters the development of texts serving various areas of communication. Accordingly, texts associated with the era of "new journalism" are marked by linguistic and stylistic diversity, as

well as the use of a wide range of visual and expressive tools. For instance, the hypertextuality of the Internet influences the language of online versions and their original content. This is particularly evident in news texts rich in specific information such as dates, names, geographic locations, organizational titles, and terminology. Thoughtfully crafted, optimized, and search engine-friendly texts attract readers, retain their attention, and facilitate faster information retrieval through keywords. Another notable feature of convergent media language is its tendency to create a written form of speech that mimics oral communication ^[6].

Texts are increasingly characterized by subjectivity, pronounced emotionality, and expressiveness. Forums, blogs, and readers' comments on journalistic texts serve as examples of simplified language in online formats, where communication often takes the form of informal dialogue. Both readers and moderator-journalists actively engage in intensive communication. Replies and comments are presented publicly and online, often with minimal editing. This explains the frequent presence of spelling and syntactic errors, as well as stylistic flaws.

In online media, neutral and expressive language elements are mixed within a single text. Another feature of such language is the tendency toward personality-oriented communication. The formal boundary between the journalist and the reader disappears, making the interaction more personal and confidential. Expressive colloquial and even vulgar language is often found in headlines. This emerging language represents a complex, multi-layered system that integrates features of all traditional media, heavily influenced by the internet. The text gains a "networked" dimension, allowing it to be perceived not only linearly but also hypertextually. This affects the creativity of journalists, the categorization and titling of content, as well as the structure and design of websites. The heterogeneity of genres in journalistic work is growing. Genres are constantly evolving and merging in media. Alongside terms like "Internet genres", synonyms such as "electronic genres", "media genres", "digital genres", and "virtual genres" are used.

In this format, the sender and recipient are equal, and communication can be interactive. Blogs combine the characteristics of journalistic writing with that of personal diaries (conversational style, written discourse genre). It is often difficult to distinguish a blog from a columnist's page if it is embedded within a site. Text authors may be journalists, experts, public figures, or ordinary individuals. Functional stylistic genres are transitioning into multimedia forms with new features and capabilities.

Convergent media use textual formats that combine elements of traditional media genres. Such platforms present various types of content – journalistic, advertising, and PR materials. The core of original journalistic content, however, typically consists of information genres such as notes, reports, correspondence, and informational interviews.

Nevertheless, there are notable differences. Editors tailor texts for online publication to fit digital formats. As a result, readers are drawn to information-focused content that is structured into concrete blocks with clear intertextual connections. On a website, only a headline or headline complex is initially visible. The full text expands through hypertext organization. Overall, informational genres are gradually displacing analytical ones. Articles and notes are divided into semantic blocks and include hyperlinks. A group of paragraphs may even have a subheading. Articles emphasize factual reporting. Essays, feuilletons, and satirical commentary remain part of the mix. Column writing is especially popular. Scientific and official-business texts, however, rarely incorporate hypertextual elements. Such texts have not significantly changed when transferred online. Purely artistic genres are underrepresented in the online versions of print media, which prioritize news content.

New personalized forms of journalist-audience interaction are emerging. A specific culture of content creation, text logic, and site design is being developed. This enhances the quality of the informational environment, fosters a culture of communication, and better meets citizens' informational and communicative needs. New technologies now allow for the distribution and consumption of far more information than before. Today, printed products are mainly used by older people or those without internet access. Print newspapers still offer benefits, such as the ability to browse an entire issue quickly, delay reading until a convenient time, and process content at one's own pace (re-reading, storing). However, they also come with drawbacks: reduced timeliness and lack of direct interactivity.

Interactivity is a core feature of electronic media and a key reason for their increasing popularity. The ability to engage in immediate dialogue with interested readers via forums, comments, or guestbooks – common on many digital platforms – fosters mutual understanding between readers and editorial staff. Through such feedback, a compelling article may evolve into a series or even a regular column.

CONCLUSION

Many internet platforms have become arenas for discussions on current issues, where users engage in conversations about the news. These websites generally show higher attendance and citation rates compared to the electronic versions of traditional print media, where journalistic texts often cannot be commented on. As a result, the chance to establish an effective feedback mechanism and a meaningful dialogue with the readership is lost.

Trust from citizens is a crucial condition for the successful functioning of the media, alongside the timely, complete, and objective presentation of information about events occurring in the regions and the country as a whole. Convergent journalism—if modern media tools are introduced into its practice in an optimal and thoughtful way—can serve as a powerful means of supporting the development of civil society, particularly in the role assigned to mass media.

Acting as a bridge for dialogue between the government and the public, the media should shape an objective understanding of reality for both parties. Through the use of feedback mechanisms and interactive platforms, readers will be able to directly share their opinions and concerns with the selected media outlets, keeping all stakeholders informed and connected to real societal issues.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

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